

FROM VR CONTROLLERS TO MULTI-USER IMMERSIVE EDUCATIONAL EXPERIENCES IN DIGITAL CULTURAL HERITAGE

The Case of Sheikh Isa House in Bahrain

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Abstract This study employs advanced virtual reality (VR) technology to reinterpret the sustainable architectural practices of Sheikh Isa House in Bahrain, offering valuable insights into immersive learning environments. Focusing on the passive solar systems of historic vernacular architecture across the Arab world, Sheikh Isa House serves as a pivotal case study. Through detailed building performance simulations, architectural features such as windcatchers, interconnected courtyards, and seasonal rooms are analyzed for their contributions to sustainability and thermal comfort. A significant advancement of this research is the transition from individual VR experiences to a multi-user immersive environment, enabling classes and groups to engage collectively within the virtual space. The VR application integrates immersive digital storytelling to facilitate an interactive exploration of regional architectural heritage and sustainable practices. Future work involves forming student focus groups to evaluate the

effectiveness of these multi-user immersive experiences compared to individual VR, aiming to enhance the educational impact of the application.

Keywords: *Digital heritage, Virtual Reality, 360 Immersive environments, Education, Sustainable heritage.*

1. Introduction

The *Sustainable Arab Heritage in VR* project (*Sustainable Heritage in VR*, 2024), initiated in 2022, seeks to harness the architectural wisdom of the past by focusing on the sustainable passive solar systems used in historic vernacular architecture across the Arab world. By analyzing these systems, the project addresses contemporary challenges related to heat management and energy consumption in today's buildings. The House of Sheikh Isa in Bahrain was chosen as the first case study for developing an educational virtual reality (VR) application designed to bring this valuable knowledge into classrooms in an engaging and interactive way. This selection underlines the strong potential of VR and augmented reality (AR) applications in design and architecture education, particularly their ability to enhance understanding of scale, proportionality, color, and materiality within a virtual environment (Guazzaroni and Pillai, 2020; Bazavan *et al.*, 2021; Vilar, Filgueiras and Rebelo, 2022; Hou *et al.*, 2024).

Building upon the foundational research from the Educational Virtual Model of Sheikh Isa House project, this paper further explores VR's transformative potential in digital cultural heritage. The initial project offered a comprehensive understanding of the building's interaction with its environmental context. It showcased the efficacy of advanced visualization techniques in communicating complex scientific data within a virtual environment. The workflow and framework established during this phase laid a solid foundation for a versatile methodology with significant implications for heritage and sustainability education. It also provided valuable insights into sustainable architectural practices applicable to contemporary contexts.

This research advances the discussion by shifting the focus from individual VR experiences to a multi-user immersive environment. This transition is pivotal in enhancing the inclusivity and accessibility of digital cultural heritage applications, particularly within educational settings such as classrooms and museums. By enabling simultaneous participation, this approach maximizes the educational

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impact of the VR application, broadening its reach and fostering deeper engagement with cultural heritage content.

By using the House of Sheikh Isa as a case study, this research aims to bridge historic architectural knowledge with contemporary technological applications. The insights gained are intended to be both practically and academically relevant, contributing to the ongoing discourse on sustainable design and digital heritage.

2. Historical Background

The house of Sheikh Isa in Bahrain was selected as the first case study for this multi-phased project. It is a historic 19th-century house located in Muharraq, the old capital of Bahrain. It is preserved in excellent condition as part of the UNESCO Pearling Path, which includes approximately 17 other buildings and extends for 2.7 miles (*Pearling, Testimony of an Island Economy*, no date; Karimi, no date). The timeline of the house saw many alterations, but the most significant period was when it served as the residence of Bahrain's ruler from 1869 to 1932, playing a significant role in Bahrain's political history (al-Khalifa and Rice, 1993; Yarwood, 2000; Yarwood and El-Masri, 2006; Al-Sulaiti, 2011).

The excellent condition of the existing structure, in addition to documentation efforts by the Bahrain Authority for Culture and Antiquities (BACA) and an international research team led by Barazzetti et al., made the house an abundant subject of study for sustainable practices in the Arab world, particularly in the Gulf region, and the methods of adaptation to the arid climate in this region (Barazzetti, Mezzino and Quintero, 2017). The structure of the house includes four connected courtyards to help circulate air inside the building, essential for privacy and internal social interaction. The house also includes a windcatcher (Figure 1), a structure commonly used in the Middle East to cool the air inside rooms. The windcatcher in the House of Sheikh Isa wasn't an integral part of the structure until it was added on top of "Al Majlis," the main living room, to help cool it down (Figure 2). This house is also a significant example of the use of native building materials, such as mudbrick, for building thick walls to help improve insulation against heat (*Bayt al-Shaykh*, n.d.; Lalande Hardy-Guilbert, 1981; Yarwood and El-Masri, 2006)

Figure 1: 3D model of the main courtyard of Sheikh Isa's house, known as the Women's Courtyard, before(left) and after(right) adding textures. The scene shows the windcatcher connected to the main living room, Al Majlis.

Figure 2: 3D visualization of the main family room, Al Majlis, directly connected to the windcatcher.

3. Project Workflow and Methodology

The workflow and framework used in the *Sustainable Heritage in VR* project, particularly in developing the educational model of Sheikh Isa House, commenced with the creation of a highly accurate 3D model of the House of Sheikh Isa in Bahrain. The model development involved using various 3D modeling software,

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including Autodesk 3DS Max and Rhino 3D, which were pivotal in ensuring the precision of the architectural details. This model was then exported to Twinmotion, where textures, materials, and lighting were applied to enhance the visual realism of the structure. Subsequently, the model was integrated into Unreal Engine 5.3('Unreal Engine 5', 2022), which served as the primary tool for developing VR educational applications, enabling further refinement and interactive capabilities.

In parallel, a second model was created using DesignBuilder software('DesignBuilder', 2023) to conduct comprehensive building performance simulations. These simulations offered critical insights into the sustainable features of the house, including thermal comfort analysis, airflow patterns through Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) (Figure 3), and daylighting analysis. The detailed analysis of airflow patterns, both inside and outside the house, revealed how the courtyards and windcatcher work in tandem to facilitate natural ventilation, efficiently cooling the interior rooms. Additionally, temperature simulations demonstrated the thermal performance of the building's materials, showcasing how traditional construction techniques effectively maintained comfortable indoor environments. Such analyses were vital in understanding the building's environmental interactions and assessing its sustainable design aspects. The results of this sustainability study are being disseminated through separate publications, providing an in-depth exploration of the findings. (Fardeheb, 2007; Hensen and Lamberts, 2011; Attia, 2014; Rajapaksha *et al.*, 2018; Al-Sallal and Rahmani, 2019; Olawale-Johnson, Ajwang and Ondimu, 2021; Ozarisoy and Altan, 2021).

Figure 3: 3D visualization of the external CFD velocity of the house of Sheikh Isa created using DesignBuilder software.

Upon acquiring the results of the sustainability study, these findings were seamlessly integrated into the virtual environment developed in Unreal Engine

5.3. This process facilitated the creation of a versatile, multi-purpose model adaptable to various outputs depending on the intended use and audience. Potential outputs include a VR application, a 360-degree video installation, and a mobile application. This workflow serves as a replicable model for similar sustainable heritage projects (Figure 4).

Figure 4. A flow diagram illustrating the integration of 3D visualization and building performance simulation results into a virtual environment, producing outputs such as a VR application, 360 video installation, and mobile application.

4. Integration with VR Environment

The building performance simulation study results were translated into a visual format and audio narration within Unreal Engine 5.3, guiding users as they explored the virtual environment. After visualizing the data, interactive elements were developed to enhance user engagement with these simulations in the VR environment. At the beginning of the experience, users are greeted with an instruction screen outlining the controls. Given the building's large size, we developed an interactive navigation map that can be opened using the buttons on the left controller. This map allows users to explore the building by selecting points of interest. By pointing at specific rooms or courtyards on the map with the suitable controller and pressing the trigger, users are instantly teleported to that area (Figure 5).

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Users can also interact with doors, opening or closing them by pointing and pressing the trigger button on the suitable controller. Sound narration is a key feature that accompanies users through different areas, providing contextual information and enhancing the user's understanding of the environment. Background audio and these audio cues play automatically to explain the environment, further enhancing immersion.

The storytelling narrative embedded within the VR application provides users with information about the house's historical background and daily usage. It also highlights the sustainable design features that contributed to its adaptation to harsh weather conditions and improved thermal comfort. The navigation map features a sustainability mode, enabling users to preview BPS results and interact with a "See in 3D" button that overlays these results onto the 3D model for enhanced immersion and understanding (Figure 5). This approach simplifies the complex scientific data generated by the building performance study, seamlessly integrating it into the VR environment to create an effective educational tool. The goal is to make intricate architectural design and sustainability concepts accessible to a broad spectrum of users, allowing students and other learners to explore these ideas in an immersive and interactive way.

Figure 5. A screenshot of the VR walkthrough created in Unreal Engine 5.3- showcasing the navigation interface map inside the educational VR model of Sheikh Isa House.

Figure 6. A screenshot showing the navigation interface map within the sustainability mode of the educational VR application, displaying a solar gain map of the main courtyard (left). The interactive feature "See in 3D" maps the solar gain data onto the 3D model, facilitating a better interpretation of the results(right).

5. Inclusive VR Immersive Experiences: Enhancing Accessibility and Engagement

The need for more inclusive VR immersive experiences became evident following rigorous testing for the demo VR application. The application was showcased at several events held at Virginia Tech University. These events attracted thousands of visitors from diverse backgrounds, including undergraduate and graduate students and individuals from the public with varying ages and experiences. This wide-ranging audience highlighted some limitations of our current VR application. Many visitors, particularly those with visual impairments, discomfort using VR headsets with eyeglasses, or physical disabilities that made it challenging to operate controllers, faced difficulties navigating the virtual environment. Additionally, in a classroom setting, the time limitations of a 75-minute lecture pose challenges in providing each student with an individual VR experience. These factors underscore the importance of developing more accessible and user-friendly VR experiences to accommodate a broader range of users and the practical constraints of educational environments (Mott *et al.*, 2019; Williams, 2022; Creed *et al.*, 2023; Dudley *et al.*, 2023).

The challenges above inspired us to explore alternative methods to involve multiple users within the immersive environment and provide a true sense of scale and proportionality. This was made possible by the availability of the Cyclorama display system, a key facility of the Institute for Creativity, Arts, and Technology (ICAT) at Virginia Tech University. Situated at the Moss Arts Center on Virginia Tech's main campus. The design of the exhibition ensured it provided a collective and inclusive experience accessible to those unable to use traditional VR devices. This immersive, interactive 360 video installation allowed a broader audience to

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engage with the VR content without the need for headsets, promoting inclusivity and accessibility for all visitors. Additionally, due to the availability of two projectors, the display system can also be previewed using stereoscopic headsets, allowing for 3D stereoscopic vision and providing users with 3D glasses. This system opens many possibilities for architecture and interior design educators who might use this system to provide their students with an unconventional method of learning about built environments, where the entire classroom could be held inside the Cyclorama (Argyriou, Economou and Bouki, 2017, 2020; Woletz *et al.*, 2018; Škola *et al.*, 2020; Weber, Weibel and Mast, 2021; Cinnamon and Jahiu, 2023) (Figure 7).

Figure 7. A 3D model depicting the structure of the Cyclorama featuring projectors, a 180-degree curved screen, and the suggested Interactive touch table

5.1. Enhancing the Immersive Experience Through Audio Narration and Storytelling

The immersive 360-degree environment is enriched by voice narration and contextual music, offering detailed explanations of key areas such as the courtyards, summer and winter rooms, the women's section, and the guest section. These narrations help participants better understand the spatial relationships and cultural significance of these spaces and their everyday use. Additionally, the voice narration succinctly presents the key findings from the building performance simulation study, providing insight into the sustainability aspects of

the design and the integration of passive solar systems within the building—an essential element of our research(Privitera, Fontana and Geronazzo, 2024).

A remarkable immersive sound system of the Cyclorama greatly improves the feeling of being present in a virtual environment. This cutting-edge audio system produces a rich acoustic landscape that flawlessly accompanies the 360-degree visual display by amplifying and enhancing sound. The precision of the voice narration and contextual music ensures that explanations of spatial relationships, cultural backgrounds, and sustainability elements are both engaging and easy to understand. This high-quality audio experience deepens user engagement and creates a more realistic and inclusive immersive environment (Figure 8).

*Figure 8. Students engaging with the 360-degree interactive, immersive installation of Sheikh Isa House at the Cyclorama in Moss Arts Center, Institute for Creativity, Arts, and Technology (ICAT), Virginia Tech University, during the exhibition *An Immersive Exploration of an Arabian Home: A Journey Through Time and Tradition*.*

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Figure 9. The interactive interface design was created with Open Stage Control, showcasing the various rooms and courtyards of the building, along with controls for adjusting the view to move right or left (right). The interface is displayed on a tablet for experimentation (left).

5.2. Cyclorama Display System

The Cyclorama display system is powered by a built-in software called "WorldViewer," developed by The Elumenati (WorldViewer, 2023). WorldViewer is widely regarded as a leading tool in the immersive media and digital display technologies industry, and it is known for its robust capabilities in managing 360-degree video media. It is frequently employed in immersive environments such as educational institutions, museums, and science centers due to its flexibility and reliability. The software allows for precise fitting and adjustment of media to match the screen's proportions, ensuring optimal visual presentation. Through extensive testing, we determined that an 8K video output provided the best resolution for the Cyclorama, significantly reducing blurriness and delivering high visual clarity.

5.3. Video Rendering and Post-Processing

The immersive experience was further enhanced through a carefully crafted sequence of 360-degree images rendered using the Sequencer in Unreal Engine 5.3. Post-processing was carried out in Adobe Premiere, where the sequence was converted into a high-quality video. Additional contextual music and voice narration layers were integrated during this stage to enrich the immersive experience, providing a more engaging and informative visual journey (Figure 10).

Figure 10. A screenshot showing the process of generating 360-degree images rendered using the Sequencer in Unreal Engine 5.3

5.4. Interaction and User-Controlled Experiences

The 360 immersive experience in this project is designed to be interactive, incorporating a touch interface displayed on a tablet (Figure 9). This interface, built using Open Stage Control, allows users to customize their experience by directly interacting with the Cyclorama display system. Open Stage Control (Open Stage Control, 2023), an open-source, modular OSC/MIDI controller, was utilized to create this seamless connection, enabling users to select different views and content for exploration directly from the tablet. This powerful software supports the creation of customizable interfaces for controlling various digital media and live performances.

In our project, Open Stage Control facilitated the development of an intuitive interface for the 360-degree video display. The software's flexibility allowed for the integration of touch interactions, including sliders for adjusting video parameters like latitude and longitude. While the tablet interface is effective for individual experimentation, we recommend a larger interactive touch table for the Cyclorama. This would allow multiple users to engage with the immersive environment simultaneously, enhancing both inclusivity and user experience. By implementing these interactive, user-controlled features, we aimed to create a more engaging educational environment that caters to a diverse audience and offers a comprehensive learning experience (Figure 10).

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Figure 11. Workflow Diagram illustrating the creation of 360 images, post-processing with audio narration, and media integration into the Cyclorama display system using Open Stage Control for interactive experiences.

5.5. Interface Design and Navigation

The interface design greatly enhances the immersive experience of the 360-degree video display. It is divided into several sections, with pictures in each section that highlight essential parts of the house, like the courtyards and the summer and winter rooms' interiors. This layout allows users to visually navigate through different parts of the house by seamlessly transitioning to the corresponding video through touch or click interactions on these images. By combining audio and visual components, this approach produces a more captivating and immersive experience. Sliders on the interface allow viewers to change the 360-degree video's latitude and longitude, giving them greater control over how they see it. This feature enables users to explore the full view of the house, even on a 180-degree curved display, mirroring the navigation capabilities of the VR application. The slider-based navigation ensures a more accessible and customizable experience, catering to different user preferences. Additionally, a reset button allows users to return to the display's initial orientation at any time (Figure 9). All voice narratives are synchronized with the interactive interface, allowing users to

learn about specific spaces at their own pace. This setup enhances the immersive experience while making it more interactive and educational.

Various WorldViewer OSC commands were employed to control the virtual environment's view for navigation functionality. The *SetLatGoal* command manages the view's latitude, or vertical angle, allowing users to adjust their viewing angle up and down within a specified range. The *SetLonGoal* command controls the longitude or horizontal angle, enabling users to pan left or right across the environment, typically within a range of -180 to +180 degrees. Additionally, the *SetTime* command was used to facilitate seamless transitions between different sections of the house tour. By assigning specific time values to other areas, users can navigate through the house's courtyards and rooms effortlessly, moving from one area to another smoothly (Open Stage Control, 2023; WorldViewer, 2023).

The interface was styled using custom CSS (Cascading Style Sheets) within Open Stage Control. The final JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) output was then integrated into the Cyclorama system, resulting in a cohesive and visually engaging user experience.

7. Scalability, Adaptability, and Educational Broader Impact

The Cyclorama display system offers a sophisticated platform for multi-user immersive experiences; however, its limited availability restricts widespread adoption. To enhance the scalability and portability of our VR system, we are actively developing adaptable solutions using more commonly accessible technologies. By leveraging standard curved screens, flat-panel displays, and multi-monitor setups, institutions can recreate 360-degree immersive environments without the need for specialized hardware.

Additionally, our interactive interface is being designed to support open-source OSC-compatible platforms and alternative control systems, ensuring compatibility with a variety of existing setups. This adaptability allows our workflow and methodology to be applied to a wide range of cultural heritage sites beyond Sheikh Isa House, enabling institutions worldwide to offer immersive experiences without prohibitive costs or technical barriers (Argyriou, Economou & Bouki, 2020). By integrating immersive technologies into diverse educational curricula, our approach supports interdisciplinary education across architecture, computer science, and history, enriching learning experiences and expanding research opportunities across these fields.

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Furthermore, we plan to make the project accessible through open-source platforms such as Open Heritage 3D (Open Heritage 3D, n.d.) and Google Arts & Culture (Google, n.d.), facilitating broader dissemination and collaboration. These platforms will allow educators, researchers, and the general public to engage with and build upon our work, thereby enhancing the preservation and dissemination of cultural heritage on a global scale. These ongoing adaptations aim to democratize access to immersive educational tools, enhance collaborative and interdisciplinary learning, and contribute significantly to preserving and disseminating cultural heritage, ensuring that historical knowledge and sustainable architectural practices are effectively communicated to future generations.

6. Conclusion & Future Work

Building upon the *Sustainable Heritage in VR* project (*Sustainable Heritage in VR*, 2024), this study advances from an individual VR-based educational model to an inclusive multi-user platform, using Sheikh Isa House in Bahrain as a central case study. Initially, our research focused on developing a VR application that provides comprehensive insights into the sustainable design elements and passive solar systems integrated within Sheikh Isa House. This application details these sustainable architectural features and serves as an educational resource for exploring the building's structural design, functional usage, and the socio-economic factors influencing its establishment and daily operations. This multifaceted approach aims to enhance learners' understanding of sustainable architectural practices and contextualize the house's historical and cultural significance, thereby offering a holistic educational experience.

Recognizing the need for collaborative and accessible learning environments in classrooms and museums, we transitioned to creating a 360-degree immersive experience using the Cyclorama system. This multi-user platform facilitates group learning, enhances accessibility, and fosters engagement, thereby democratizing access to cultural heritage. We are forming a student focus group to evaluate the effectiveness of the VR application compared to the immersive 360-degree installation. Additionally, the project is expanding to include a comparative analysis of a similar building in the Arab Gulf region, focusing on sustainability practices and architectural techniques. By enabling interactive navigation between these buildings, we aim to deepen the understanding of regional architectural variations. Furthermore, we plan to make the project accessible through open-

source platforms, facilitating broader dissemination and collaboration. These efforts strive to create more inclusive, engaging, and educational immersive experiences, benefiting diverse educational, cultural, and museum applications.

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